

Geospatial Assessment of Potential Groundwater Zones Within Igede Ekiti, Ekiti State, Nigeria

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Suggested Citation

Odesola, O.O. & Ogunlade, S.O. (2024). Geospatial Assessment of Potential Groundwater Zones Within Igede Ekiti, Ekiti State, Nigeria. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 2(3), 809-821.

DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2024.2\(3\).63](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2024.2(3).63)

Abstract:

Groundwater happens to be an accessible and renewable source of water, and so has to be monitored. A Multi-criteria Decision approach was utilized which allows for data fusion of various thematic criteria using the Analytical Hierarchical approach to assign weight to the selected criteria peculiar to Igede-Ekiti, of Irepodun/Ifelodun Local Government Area. The study aims to carry out a geospatial assessment of the groundwater potential zone within Igede Ekiti, Ekiti state. Geology, Rainfall, Digital Elevation Model, Land Use land cover, Nominal difference in water Index (NDWI), Slope and Lineament density were selected to depict the potential

groundwater zones, of which geospatial assessments were carried out. Selected groundwater sources in the form of boreholes and well were afterwards used to ground truth and depict the distribution of groundwater sources within the study area. The ArcMap software's weight overlay Analysis was used to present the output in the form of a Potential Groundwater zones (PGWZ) map, with the Groundwater sources, wells and boreholes, indicating that they were well dispersed within the study area, but more densely situated around the built-up class of the study area. The results indicate that high PGWZ was more prevalent than the other classes, as the classes were distributed into very high, high and low PGWZ. The very high PGWZ covered 7%, the high PGWZ 55% and the Low PGWZ, 38%. The study can be used for further physical planning and decision-making for policymakers. Further research into the Spatio-temporal behaviour of groundwater potential is recommended.

Keywords: *Analytical Hierarchical process (AHP), Groundwater, Remote Sensing, data fusion.*

Introduction

A crucial component of the water cycle is groundwater. The subsurface absorbs some of the precipitation that falls on the surface. The fraction of groundwater recharge that passes through the soil and into saturated rock material. While surface water refers to drainage systems and features of hydrologic, geomorphologic, and

climatic processes, groundwater is the subterranean water that occurs below the water level in fully saturated soils and geologic formations and is gravitationally regulated (Tijani, 2017). Assuring a steady and sustainable supply of drinking groundwater is one of the most crucial aspects of a nation's sustainable development (Li, 2021). The main sources of

water for humans in the past were rainwater, streams, and lakes. However, due to human-caused pollution and contamination they can be unfit for consumption. (Olorunfemi et al, 1999). Compared to surface water, groundwater is typically less costly, more practical, and less prone to pollution. As a result, it is widely utilized for the delivery of municipal water (National Geographic Almanac of Geography, 2005).

Groundwater is commonly used in Nigeria for domestic, agricultural, and industrial purposes. Water availability per person was 1,536 m³ per year in 2015 with a population of 182.2 million; this number is expected to drop to 1,175 m³ in 2025 with a predicted population of 238.4 million. Only 63% of Nigeria's boreholes were active, with many of them out of service due to pump failure, according to a 1996 Ministry of Water Resources assessment. For residential water delivery, one borehole might provide 230–500 people who lived within 500 meters of the water source. Given that 52% of the population lives in rural regions supplied by hand-pump boreholes, Nigeria would require at least 190,000 boreholes (Jamiu, 2020).

In order to help decision-makers deal with the geographically complex problem of environmental concerns, the Analytic Hierarchy Process is a multi-criteria decision-making analysis (Zolekar and Bhagat, 2015). There have been several studies done in order to identify a potential groundwater zone. Based on their respective importance in the decision-making process to define four groundwater zones, the weights of each attribute were established. The main benefits of AHP include accuracy, cost-effective and time-efficient results, and hierarchical formulation (Das, 2019). When this occurs, the AHP technique is successfully used globally to manage water resources. An important asset of AHP is its quantitative and qualitative approach (Forman, 1993). In Igede Ekiti, Ekiti state, the study's goal is to conduct a geospatial assessment of the groundwater potential zone. Given that it is the most dependable source of water for agriculture, groundwater is crucial to humanity. According to research on sustainability and intelligent

exploitation, there is a correlation between groundwater availability and a drop in farmer poverty (Adebola, 2016; Moench, 2000). As a result, it is crucial that groundwater resources continue to be available.

The Estimation of the Groundwater Storage and Its Distribution in Uzbekistan is one of the literatures that was evaluated for this project. A map showing the amount of groundwater in the research region was developed as a result of the study by Wahyuni et al. (2008), which set out to calculate the volume of groundwater within its storage using conventional geophysical techniques. Instead of using a GIS, the investigation takes a conventional geophysical approach. Owolabi et al. (2020) aimed to utilize a geoscience approach for mapping high-precision GWPZs (Groundwater Potential Zones) particular to the semi-arid region. They used Buffalo catchment, Eastern Cape, South Africa as their test site. Weightage priority at a constituency ratio of 0.087 was the result of this method. Bayowa et al., (2014) in "Integration of Hydro geophysical and Remote Sensing Data in the Assessment of Groundwater Potential of the Basement Complex Terrain of Ekiti State, Southwest Nigeria," the authors sought to classify the area into various groundwater potential zones by conducting hydro geophysical investigation as well as analyses of hydro-geomorphological condition of Ekiti State's groundwater potential is typically rated as being at a very low to moderate level. However, there were only a small number of sites with high to very high groundwater potential and more study gaps that need additional research for variations within regions to more effectively target smaller communities. A study on the Assessment of Groundwater Potential Zones Using GIS Technique was conducted by Singh V.P. & Singh, S. (2006). This research attempts to identify and map locations with high potential for groundwater occurrence and abstraction in a specific region. In order to create a thorough groundwater potential map, the study employs GIS (Geographic Information System) to combine and analyze numerous data layers, including geology, topography, soil, land use, and hydrological factors. Al-Ozeer *et al.* (2021)

emphasised that planning the sustainable management of groundwater resources can greatly benefit from knowledge of the groundwater potential, particularly in a dry environment. Nine machine learning (ML) algorithms were used in this study to model the groundwater potential, including the Artificial Neural Network (ANN), Decision Jungle (DJ), Averaged Perceptron (AP), Bayes Point Machine (BPM), Decision Forest (DF), Locally-Deep Support Vector Machine (LD-SVM), Boosted

Decision Tree (BDT), Logistic Regression (LG), and Support Vector Machine (SVM). Five groundwater potential zones—very low, low, moderate, high, and very high—corresponding to the northern (very low to low), southern (moderate), and middle (high to high) groundwater potential probabilities—were mapped and visualized using these techniques.

Figure 1. Map of Nigeria Showing Ekiti State Showing Igede-Ekiti

Study Area

The study area is Igede-Ekiti, a town within the Ifelodun / Irepodun local government of Ekiti State, Nigeria. Igede-Ekiti is located within longitude 5°6'E and longitude 5°9'E of the equator and Latitude 7°39'N and 7°42'N of the Greenwich meridian. Irepodun/Ifelodun Local Government Area has its administrative headquarters in Igede town, comprising of the towns and villages of Igede-Ekiti, Iyin-Ekiti, Igbemo-Ekiti, Awo-Ekiti, Afao, Are, Awo, Igbemo, Iropora / Esure / Eyio Iworoko and Aramoko-Ekiti.

Igede Ekiti climatic conditions have a generous annual rainfall of about 400mm with a low coefficient variation of about 30% during the rainfall peak months, with an average of about 112 rainy days per annum and a very stable weather conditions usually wet within the February to October and dry within November to January. The rocks are dominated by crystalline rocks, forming parts of South-Western Nigeria's basement complex geology (Adebayo, 1993). Below in Figure 1 is the study area map.

Materials and Methods

The data sets used for the study were the thematic map of the factors considered in the multi-criteria decision analysis carried out using the Weight overlay Analysis tool of the ArcGIS 10.5 software, alongside the coordinate information of the groundwater sources used in the course of this study.

The primary data used were the Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS) coordinates and the status of wells and boreholes gotten.

The secondary data used were the Landsat imagery of 30m accuracy and DEM data (30m accuracy) of the study area to be downloaded from the USGS (United States Geological Survey), NASA Earthdata to obtain SRTM DEM data and the TRMM website for the rainfall dataset, alongside the other thematic layers used for the weight overlay analysis, which consists of LULC, NDWI(Normalized difference in water index), Slope, Lineament density and rainfall data, all these factors were considered as criteria for determining the Potential groundwater zones (PGWZ).

Table 1. Data Used

S/N	DATA	SOURCE	YEAR	RESOLUTION
1	Landsat 8 OLI/TIRS	United States Geological survey (USGS)	2022	30m
2	Rainfall	TRMM (Tropical rainfall measuring mission)	2002 - 2022	30m
3	Administrative map	Local Government Office,	2023	1:30,000
4	GPS Coordinates	Field Survey	2023	50cm
5	Landuse/ Landcover	Esri Living atlas	2022	10m
6	Digital Elevation model (DEM)	NASA earthdata (SRTM)	2013	30m
7	Geology Map of Ekiti state.	Department of Remote Sensing & Geosciences Information System (FUTA).	2023	1: 250,000

Analytical Hierarchy Process

This was used to determine the hierarchy of the factors and thematic layers that would determine the arrangement of the layers. This was needed for the overlay analysis by the weighted overlay analysis (WOA), this is very important for the algorithm of the WOA tool to determine the

PGWZ. The AHP was done using Klaus Goepel's model of the analytical hierarchical model developed in the form of an Excel spreadsheet file software which will be used to present the various factors into their hierarchy of importance and influence, and consequently the

scale value. This tool simplifies the pairwise comparison tool.

Preprocessing

The pre- Processing involves making the various data set fit and conform to their various extent for proper processing. The methodology for preprocessing all of the thematic layers that serve as criteria in determining the Groundwater Potential Zones (GWPZ) would be itemized below.

- i. CLIPPING: All the data set which consists of the Digital elevation model, Rainfall, slope, hill shade, Nominal difference in water index (NDWI) and Land use Land cover (LULC) maps are all to be pre-processed using the clip tool of the data management toolbox of the ArcGIS Software.
- ii. DENSITY OPERATION: Digitizing of the lineament starts the process of hill shade of varying degrees and carrying out the density analysis of the spatial analyst tool to generate the lineament density layer.

iii. CONVERSION OPERATION: to generate the rainfall layer properly to be used for the analysis, the downloaded rainfall raster data set is imported into the ArcGIS environment and the point digitizing tool is used to select high number of dense points within the raster data set according to the varying degrees of each value of rainfall which comes prior to the raster to point operation. The Raster to point tool of the Conversion toolbox was used to carry out this operation.

iv. INTERPOLATION: the points generated from the above operation will then be used to generate the final rainfall layer to be used in the Weigh overlay analysis, by making use of the kriging interpolation tool. This tool can be found under the Spatial analyst tool.

Visualization

Table 2 gives a detailed description of the maps shown in Figure 2 – Figure 8

Table 2. Criteria Breakdown into Classes Used for Analysis

FACTOR		CLASS	AREA (SQ. KM)	PERCENTAGE
LULC				
	BARELAND	1	5.49	6.9%
	VEGETATION	2	72.6	90.7%
	BUILT UP AREA	3	1.98	2.5%
NDWI				
	HIGH (-0.212 to -0.1579)	1	11.83	14.8%
	MODERATE (-0.158 to -0.138)	2	31.98	39.9%
	LOW (-0.138 to -0.0706)	3	36.25	45.3%
RAINFALL				
	HIGH	1	4.35	5.4%
	MODERATE	2	27.094	33.8%
	MODERATE	3	39.77	49.7%
	LOW	4	8.86	11.1%
SLOPE				
	HIGH (12.454 – 36.499m)	1	36.11	45.09%
	MODERATE (6.44 – 12.453m)	2	33.25	41.52%
	LOW (0 – 6.4m)	3	10.73	13.40%
DEM				
	HIGH (556.000 – 670.000m)	1	14.09	17.6%
	MODERATE (514.001 – 556.000m)	2	30.87	38.6%
	LOW (432 – 514m)	3	35.11	43.8%
LINE DENS				
	HIGH (1.98 – 2.98)	1	3.63	4.5%
	MODERATE (0.993 -1.986)	2	5.48	6.8%
	LOW (0 – 0.99m)	3	70.98	88.6%

GEOLOGY				
	Undifferentiated Schist with Phyllite and amphibolitic layers (SC)	1	6.01	7.5%
	Charnockitic Rocks (CH)	2	6.25	7.8%
	Magmatic Rocks(M)	3	67.86	84.7%

Figure 2. Rainfall of the Study Area

Figure 3. NDWI of the Study Area

Figure 4. LULC of the Study Area

Figure 5. Lineament Density Study Area

Figure 6. Geological Map of Study Area

Figure 7. DEM of the Study Area

Figure 8. Slope of the Study Area

Figure 9 (in Appendix) describes in percentage the coverage of the features within the study area of each criteria considered for the analysis. Class 1 showed high priority, followed by class 2 and class 3 was given least priority. The higher the priority the more favorable for potential groundwater, hence higher tendency.

Figure 9 (in Appendix) gives a breakdown of the classes the various factors were divided into for the weight overlay analysis. The AHP result as seen in figure 10 consists of the seven criteria used as factors that include rainfall, Land Use land cover (LULC), Digital elevation model (DEM), Slope, Nominal Difference in water

index (NDWI), lineament Density and Geology. The result shows a consistency index of 7.3 which indicates consistency for matrix of 5x5

and above, below in figure 11 is the graph of the weights assigned to the factors listed above.

AHP Analytic Hierarchy Process (EVM multiple inputs)

K. D. Goepel Version 15.09.2018 Free web based AHP software on: <http://bpmsg.com>

Only input data in the light green fields and worksheets!

n= Number of criteria (2 to 10) Scale: AHP 1-9
 N= Number of Participants (1 to 20) α : Consensus:
 p= selected Participant (0=consol.) 2 7 Consolidated

Objective TO DETERMINE WEIGHTAGES TO ASSIGN TO VARIOUS FACTORS RESPONSIBLE FOR POTENTIAL GWZ

Author GBOTEMI

Date 31/03/2022 Thresh: 1E-08 Iterations: 6 EVM check: 1.4E-09

Table	Criterion	Comment	Weights	+/-
1	RAINFALL		30.8%	7.9%
2	LULC		2.4%	1.1%
3	DEM		6.6%	2.5%
4	SLOPE		8.6%	2.8%
5	NDWI		3.9%	2.3%
6	LINE. DENSITY		13.7%	8.2%
7	GEOLOGY		34.0%	14.2%
8			0.0%	0.0%
9		for 9&10 unprotect the input sheets and expand the question section ("+" in row 66)	0.0%	0.0%
10			0.0%	0.0%

Result	Eigenvalue	Lambda: 7.586	MRE: 44.9%
	Consistency Ratio	0.37 GCI: 0.26 Psi: 2.9% CR: 7.3%	

Figure 10. AHP Result

Geology takes precedence as the major factor considered in determining groundwater potential zones, this is because the geological condition is highly crucial in depicting the nature of the aquifer which stores water and porosity level followed by rainfall which supplies the aquifer, next is the lineament density that depicts the faults, cracks that allows water sip into the ground and serve as a route to the groundwater

source, followed by the slope and DEM that depicts the runoff nature, followed by the LULC and the NDWI depicting the activities, division of land features and nature of the surface water and plant water content respectively. All these factors were considered in the analysis to determine the potential groundwater zones within the study area, the thematic description has been illustrated in figure 2-8 above.

Figure 11. Graph Showing the Weight Assigned

The potential groundwater zones were divided into very high, high and low potential groundwater zones, with the very high covering 7%, the high covering 54.6% which occupies the

most within the study area and the low occupying 6.9% of the study areas shown in the graph in figure 12.

Figure 12. Graph Depicting the Distribution of the Potential Groundwater Zones

Figure 13. Potential Groundwater Zones Map Showing Groundwater Sources within the Study Area

The groundwater sources are dispersed throughout the study area, though they are nucleated within the built-up area. The result in Figure 13 above indicates that 24 groundwater source fell among the 32 selected points fell within the high potential groundwater zones, while 8 fell within the low potential groundwater show and none within the very high potential groundwater zone because it is at the outskirts of the town and has little development to allow for habitation, it is sounded more by thick vegetation.

Accuracy = (The number of correctly positioned groundwater source points)/(Total number of groundwater source points) * 100

$$\text{Accuracy} = 28/32 * 100 = 87.5\%$$

This shows that the accuracy of the produced map having been validated by the groundwater source points in the course of the study is 87.5%, showing the potential groundwater zones (GPWZ) map is of high quality and truly reliable.

Geospatial Assessment using Remote sensing and techniques and statistical approach such as the Analytical hierarchical process tool proved fast, affordable and reliable. Based on the outcome of this research, it can be concluded that high Potential Groundwater potential zones is more predominant within the study area.

Conclusion

Based on the results obtained in this research, the major conclusions are as follows;

- The result of the data fusion of various thematic criteria as selected peculiar to the study area were able to help provide a multicriteria decision model as seen in the result shown in the previous chapter to give a reliable geospatial assessment as in this case of Potential Groundwater zones.
- The result shows that the high potential area dominated more within the study area, followed by the low potential groundwater zones and finally the very high potential groundwater zones.
- The study area (Igede -Ekiti) has shown from other researches is an area of low potential groundwater zone relative to Ekiti state compared to Aramoko-Ekiti which happens to be high, hence the reason for the tendency as seen from the model map produced that the very high potential groundwater zone is where it is positioned due to its proximity to Aramoko-Ekiti (Bayowa et al., 2014).
- The ground truthing data shows accuracy of 87.5% of the model map from the 32 groundwater sources presented.
- The distribution of the groundwater within the study area is clustered more within the built-up area due to the presence of residential buildings and housing and in general the study area.

- Some notable locations within the Study area with good PGWZ are Odo-uri, Ilogbo, and vicinity towards Iyin-Ekiti, while for the very high PGWZ is towards the outskirts bordering Aramoko- Ekiti, while low for the PGWZ is most of the other residential areas around Ilamoye quarters of the study area.

Recommendations

Based on the results obtained in this research, the major recommendation are as follows;

- There should be more development around the very high potential Groundwater zones to aid in more exploration of the resources and reduce pressure on the other areas.
- The very high Groundwater potential Zone should be explored and study done to ascertain if it can be a source for the water works that has stopped functioning, and more funding should go into maintenance of the water works structure.
- The groundwater source distribution indicates clustered pattern; however, proper regulation should be done to reduce tendency of highly clustered and poor constructed boreholes or wells so as to prevent natural disasters like landslides.
- The model map produced should also be adopted in the master planning of the study area for the future.

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Appendix

Figure 9. Class Distribution of the Thematic Criteria Considered